

Selective Chlorination of Chrysin using $[\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_3\text{Cl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$ Complex

NAZNEEN PARVEEN^a, NIZAM U. KHAN^a, B. ACHARI^b and P. K. DUTTA^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

^bIndian Institute of Chemical Biology, 4 Raja S. C. Mullik Road, Calcutta-700 032

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The residual insecticides in food and feed are health hazard. Therefore, there is an increased interest in the search for biodegradable insecticides of natural origin¹. Attempts have been made earlier to prepare chloro derivatives of natural flavones by the use of either sulphuryl chloride, leading to the chlorination of both the benzene rings as well as heterocyclic ring², or iron(III) chloride in presence of perchloric acid and acetic acid leading to chlorination of only A-ring³. The results⁵ of attempted chlorination of a natural flavone, chrysin, with $[\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_3\text{Cl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$ ⁴ have been presented in this communication. The reaction of chrysin with this reagent led to the selective nuclear chlorination of ring-A at positions 6 and 8, yielding 6-chloro-, 8-chloro- and 6,8-dichlorochrysin. The use of equimolar ratio of chrysin and iron-complex led to the total recovery of the substrate, whereas the use of 5-fold iron-complex gave 22% of 6,8-dichlorochrysin. The maximum yield of the chlorinated products (60%) was obtained by the use of 10-fold reagent, giving 6-chlorochrysin (**3**; 21%), 6,8-dichlorochrysin (**4**; 18%) and 8-chlorochrysin (**5**; 21%) which were identified as their methyl ethers.

Experimental

As a typical procedure, $[\text{Fe}(\text{DMF})_3\text{Cl}_2][\text{FeCl}_4]$ complex (5.44 g, 10 mmol), prepared following a reported procedure⁴, dissolved in water and chrysin (0.254 g, 1 mmol) dissolved in ether, were mixed and the mixture was

refluxed with stirring for 1 h. It was then poured in dilute HCl and the product extracted with ethyl acetate. The crude product (0.25 g) obtained from the EtOAc extract, was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone in the usual way.

The products were separated by column chromatography. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave a mixture of two compounds (**3** and **4**), which were separated by prep-tlc (SiO₂; benzene-acetone, 9 : 1). Compound **3** gave white crystals, m.p. 195–96° (CHCl₃-EtOH), *R_f* 0.58 cm⁻¹, fluorescence in uv-light, ν_{max} 1 630, 1 590, 1 445, 1 342 and 1 210 cm⁻¹, δ (CDCl₃) 4.02 (3H, s, 7-OCH₃), 4.05 (3H, s, 5-OCH₃), 6.72 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.89 (1H, s, 8-H), 7.58 (3H, m, 3',5'-H), 7.91 (2H, dd, *J* 7 and 3 Hz, 2',6'-H), *m/z* 316 (100%, M⁺, C₁₇H₁₃O₄Cl). From these data it was characterised as 6-chloro-5,7-dimethoxyflavone. Compound **4** had m.p. 215° (CHCl₃), *R_f* 0.70, fluorescence in uv-light, *m/z* 350 (M⁺, 100%). It was thus characterised as 6,8-dichloro-5,7-dimethoxyflavone (**4**).

Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) again gave a mixture of chrysin and another product which were separated by prep-tlc (SiO₂; benzene-acetone, 3 : 2). Chrysin was recovered in 40% yield. The other compound **5** had m.p. 256–57° (CHCl₃-EtOH), *R_f* 0.4, green fluorescence in uv-light, ν_{max} 1 635, 1 445, 1 340, 1 205, 1 130 and 1 090 cm⁻¹, δ (CDCl₃) 4.04 (3H, s, 7-OCH₃), 4.08 (3H, s, 5-OCH₃), 6.49 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.75 (1H, s, 6-H), 7.59 (3H, m, 3',4',5'-H), 8.0 (2H, dd, *J* 7 and 3 Hz, 2',6'-H), *m/z* 136 (M⁺, 100%). It was thus characterised as 8-chloro-5,7-dimethoxyflavone (**5**).

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